

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Malonic Acid, Induced by Potassium Permanganate. Part I

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The period of induction in the reduction of mercuric chloride by malonic acid, induced by potassium permanganate, has been found to decrease with the increase in the concentration of any of the reactants and temperature. The influence of the concentration of the reactants on the amount of mercuric chloride reduced has also been studied. Inorganic acids, viz, HCl, HNO₃, and H₂SO₄, have been found to retard the reaction; acetic acid exerts no effect.

Activation of oxalic acid by oxidising agents, such as potassium permanganate, potassium persulphate, etc., exhibited in the ready reduction of mercuric chloride to mercurous state, was first observed by Dhar¹. Saxena and Singhal² studied the induction period of the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid, induced by potassium persulphate. The present communication deals with the dependence of the induction period on the temperature and the concentration of the reactants and the relationship among the amounts of the inductor (KMnO₄), actor (malonic acid), and acceptor (HgCl₂) on the total amount of calomel formed. The influence of different acids on the reduction of mercuric chloride has also been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure.—The flasks containing the reaction mixture were kept in a thermostat, maintained at the desired temperature. After 120 min., the precipitated mercurous chloride was filtered through a double-walled funnel at ice-water temperature to arrest the reaction. It was then estimated volumetrically by titrating against a standard potassium iodate solution³. The time between mixing of the reactants and the first appearance of mercurous chloride precipitate was noted as the period of induction.

Fig. 1 and 2 show respectively the dependence of the induction period and the amount of calomel formed (or mercuric chloride reduced) in 2hr. on the concentration of the reactants at 25°. The influence of different acids, viz., HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, and acetic acid, on the reduction of mercuric chloride is shown in Fig. 4.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 690; this *Journal*, 1928, 6, 203.

2. This *Journal*, 1961, 38, 863.

3. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis".

For curves 1 (Fig. 1 and 2), the initial concentrations of mercuric chloride and potassium permanganate were kept $0.01 M$ and that of malonic acid was varied. For curves 2, the concentration of mercuric chloride was varied, but those of malonic acid and potassium permanganate were kept $0.1 M$ and $0.01 M$ respectively. Curves 3 show the variation of the concentration of potassium permanganate, keeping the concentrations of mercuric chloride and malonic acid unchanged, i.e. $0.01 M$ and $0.1 M$ respectively. For Fig. 4 the concentrations of malonic acid, mercuric chloride, and potassium permanganate were $0.1 M$, $0.01 M$, and $0.01 M$ respectively. To study the influence of different inorganic acids on the reduction of mercuric chloride, different amounts of the acid were added in the reaction mixture. Fig. 3 shows the variation of the induction period when the concentrations of malonic acid, mercuric chloride, and potassium permanganate were kept at $0.1 M$, $0.01 M$, and $0.01 M$ respectively and the temperature was varied from 10° to 45° .

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows that increase of concentration of any of the reactants decreases the period of induction. Similar observation was also noted by Saxena and Singhal² in the case of potassium persulphate used as an inductor. The reduction of mercuric chloride has been found to increase, though not proportionally, with the increase of concentration of any of the reactants.

Neither $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ nor MnO_4^- ion alone is able to reduce mercuric chloride, but a mixture of the two does so. This clearly suggests that as a result of interaction of the two

ions, some active product is produced which reduces Hg^{2+} ion to Hg_2^{2+} . This active product is probably the CO_2^- radical:

which may be formed during the further oxidation of oxalic acid, formed itself in the oxidation of malonic acid by potassium permanganate during the course of the reaction. This view is supported by the fact that oxalic acid is produced when malonic is oxidised by permanganate⁴ and the CO_2^- radical is formed, as has been observed in the oxidation of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate⁵ and halogens⁶.

The period of induction is the time required for the formation of the complex⁷, $\text{K}_3\text{Mn}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_3$ and its subsequent thermal decomposition to Mn^{3+} to produce $\text{CH}(\text{COOH})_2$ radical, resulting finally in the the production of CO_2^- radical responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride. An increase in temperature decomposes the complex earlier and thereby the period of induction is decreased, as shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3. Variation of I. P. with temp.

FIG. 4. Influence of diff. acids on the reduction of HgCl_2 .

Fig. 4 shows that acetic acid has practically no effect on the reduction of mercuric chloride, whereas HCl , HNO_3 , and H_2SO_4 retard reduction. The retarding effect is in the following order: $\text{HCl} > \text{HNO}_3 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$

Ionisation of these acids is in the same order. Fig. 4 also shows that on increasing the concentration of the acids (HCl , HNO_3 & H_2SO_4), the retardation also increases. This is again due to the increase in the hydrogen-ion concentration.

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